

A MODIFICATION OF THE GUARESCHI PYRIDINE SYNTHESIS. PART III

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Synthesis of certain pyridine derivatives by the reaction of benzylidene-esters and-ketones with cyanoacetamide and aminoacrylonitriles are described.

In the earlier communications it has been shown that cyanoacetamide and β amino- β -arylacrylonitriles react with benzylidene-acetoacetic ester and benzylidene-cyanoacetic ester to give various pyridine derivatives (this *Journal*, 1937, 15, 219, 354). The reaction has now been extended to benzylidene-malonic ester and benzylidene-cyclohexanone with similar results. With diethylamine as the condensing agent, the former reacted with cyanoacetamide to give a diethylammonium salt of diketopiperidine (I), while if sodium ethoxide was used, the normal dihydro-oxyppyridine (II) resulted.

(I) is easily transformed into (II) by heating for a few minutes with dilute HCl, whereas hot caustic soda opens up the pyridine ring with the formation of diethylamine and ammonia.

The aminoacrylonitriles were much less reactive, diethylamine having failed to bring about the reaction. With sodium ethoxide, the molecule decomposed liberating benzaldehyde which reacted with two molecules of the acrylonitrile to give (III), described previously by Meyer (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1908, II, 591). The reaction was more fruitful with Kohler and Souther's reagent (few drops of sodium methoxide in absolute methyl alcohol, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 2903).

on standing in ice. These were filtered and twice crystallised from alcohol as elongated plates (under the microscope), m.p. 179° (Found: C, 63.0; H, 4.55; N, 10.1. $C_{15}H_{13}O_4N_2$ requires C, 63.39; H, 4.23; N, 9.85 per cent).

(b) *With β -Amino-p-anisylacrylonitrile: Formation of 5-Cyano-3-carbethoxy-4-phenyl-6-anisyl-2-oxy-pyridine.*—Molecular quantities of the reactants were dissolved in absolute methyl alcohol and two drops of a solution of sodium methoxide in methyl alcohol added. It was allowed to stand for two weeks, boiled under reflux for four hours and again allowed to stand. A shining white, wooly, crystalline mass separated. It is insoluble in sodium carbonate but soluble in caustic soda from which acids reprecipitate it. It was recrystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 204°. (Found: N, 7.82. $C_{22}H_{18}O_4N_2$ requires N, 7.5 per cent).

(c) *With β -Amino-p-tolylacrylonitrile.*—As above, the mixture was allowed to stand for two weeks, boiled and again allowed to stand. It was recrystallised from methyl alcohol in mesh of needles, m.p. 208°. (Found: N, 8.2. $C_{22}H_{18}O_3N_2$ requires N, 7.82 per cent).

Reactions of Benzylidene-cyclohexanone

(a) *With Cyanoacetamide: (i) Formation of 9-Hydroxy-3-cyano-4-phenyldecahydro-2-quinolone.*—The ketone was added to a hot alcoholic solution of the amide and diethylamine added. The mixture was kept warm for 3 hours. The colour very gradually deepened from yellow to yellowish brown. Next day a small amount of crystals deposited at the bottom (m.p. 156°) which dissolved in water and caustic soda and evolved ammonia on warming with the latter suggesting it to be an open-chain addition product. After a few days the solution showed a strong yellow-green fluorescence. The solvent was evaporated off and the residual gummy mass was crystallised from ethyl acetate as hard nodules, m.p. 265-68° with shrinking and turning brown. It is insoluble in hot water but soluble in hot NaOH from which HCl regenerates it. It was recrystallised from alcohol in light, pointed, microscopic lancets, m.p. 272°. (Found: N, 10.66. $C_{16}H_{16}O_2N_2$ requires N, 10.37 per cent).

(ii) *Formation of 3-Cyano-2-oxy-4-phenyl-ar-tetrahydroquinoline.*—Sodium (0.23 g.) was used in absolute alcoholic solution with molecular quantities of the reactants. Colour gradually changed and fluorescence developed. The solvent was evaporated off and the sticky residue rubbed with water and allowed to stand overnight. The white solid so obtained (2 g.) was crystallised from a large volume of alcohol, m.p. 257-58° (Found: N, 11.42. $C_{16}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 11.20 per cent).

(b) *With β -Amino-p-tolylacrylonitrile: Formation of 3-Cyano-4-phenyl-5-tolyl-ar-tetrahydroquinoline.*—It was prepared as above. After standing for a week the solid deposited was collected and washed with hot water and crystallised from alcohol in yellow nodules, m.p. 196°. (Found: N, 8.81. $C_{23}H_{20}N_2$ requires N, 8.64 per cent).